

Review Article

Development of Henri Fayol's Principles of Management on the Implementation of Governance in the Banking Industry in Indonesia

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Abstract

This article aims to explain the development of management theory, especially Henri Fayol's management principles, which became a new phenomenon in 1916. Henri Fayol's management principles led to changes in the company's management system, not only in terms of company management but also contributed to the role of managers in a company so that managers can carry out management functions such as planning, organizing, directing, coordinating and controlling so that company goals are achieved. This principle should still be relevant today, where the development of information technology continues to advance. Of course, Henri Fayol's management principles will improve the quality of company management and corporate governance. This article will discuss the development of management principles by Henri Fayol in implementing control in the banking industry in Indonesia because, as an industry that manages public funds, it is essential to implement good governance and management principles. This research uses descriptive qualitative analysis methods. Henri Fayol's contribution to management science, especially in corporate governance in the Indonesian banking sector, has significantly impacted the understanding and implementation of management principles. Fayol's principles, such as esprit de corps, initiative, unity of direction, authority and responsibility, remuneration, division of work, and discipline, help create a work environment that is harmonious, productive, and oriented towards common goals. Implementing sound corporate governance by combining these principles can increase transparency, accountability, and overall performance in the Indonesian banking sector, maintain stakeholder trust, and ensure business continuity amidst economic dynamics and changes in the business environment—Development principles. This article discusses several literature articles and then concludes whether the development of Henri fayol's management principles has a role in corporate governance applied to the Indonesian banking industry.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Henri Fayol, Literature Study, Management Principles.

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Introduction

The development of management science always experiences evolution over time, following the demands of the business world. Management science developed rapidly due to the role of essential figures in America and France, such as Frederick W. Taylor and Henri Fayol (Immanuel et al., 2022). The evolution of management science can be broken down into five primary paradigm shifts based on Thomas Kuhn's definition of paradigm. Each management theory created new beliefs and introduced new laws in the 20th century. Five main paradigm changes in its development can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Evolution of Management Theory

The first stage was the scientific management period (1910s), where Frederick Taylor introduced this first paradigm. Taylor changed the view of management as a science. Taylor emphasized the specialization of tasks and division of work to increase efficiency. This thinking marked a shift from a focus on machines to an emphasis on increasing labor productivity. Taylor proposed scientific management principles to improve training, skill building, and fair distribution of tasks (Khorasani & Almasifard, 2017). The evolution of this paradigm represents a revolution in understanding the role of labor and management, providing the basis for the first systematic studies of human behavior in the workplace (Ratnayake, 2009). Taylor's paradigm encouraged breaking down tasks into minor units and finding the best way to carry them out, creating the foundation for scientific management thinking (Khorasani & Almasifard, 2017; Kuhn, 1970). When Frederick Taylor introduced Scientific Management, almost simultaneously, Henri Fayol and Max Weber formulated a new paradigm in management theory known as administrative management theory. Fayol and Weber focused on organizational and practical management aspects. Although Fayol had an engineering background, he realized management involved more than simply improving output and designing systems. Fayol, while becoming general manager, developed his managerial principles (Wren & Bedeian, 2009), which are described as a set of rules, methods, and procedures. Henri Fayol is one of the founders of modern management science, who discovered five management functions to achieve expected goals (Fayol, 2013; Witzel, 2003) and 14 management principles (Fayol, 2013; Rahman, 2012). Apart from Fayol, Max Weber also contributed

significantly to his theory of bureaucracy. This theory emphasizes a hierarchical organizational structure, with authority organized in specific areas of activity, actions governed by rules, training for experts in the field, and application of regulations by neutral officials. Together, Fayol and Weber brought a new perspective to management that placed greater emphasis on organizational effectiveness and administrative structure.

The third stage of development occurred before the Second World War; pioneers such as Mary Parker Follet played a vital role in developing the humanistic management perspective. Follet focuses on the interaction between management and labor, defining management as executing tasks through people. Follet promoted direct communication between managers from different departments and encouraged worker participation in job development, making her the mother of conflict resolution. Behavioral theories developed by Hawthorn, Maslow, and McGregor between 1940 and 1970 developed this view further. The essence of perspective Humanistics encompasses the human relations movement, the human resources perspective, and behavioral science approaches. Behavioral management theory creates a meeting point between management and behavioral science, emphasizing worker motivation as an organization's primary goal. This view reflects a paradigm shift toward recognizing human value and the role of emotions in management contexts. The fourth stage of the development of management science occurred after the Second World War. In this period, management science experienced significant growth using the adoption of mathematics, statistical techniques, and quantitative approaches as the main factors. Operations research, quality control, inventory management, and information technology are the main focuses in the management discipline. One of the leading figures in this development was Edward Deming, the father of quality management (Khorasani & Almasifard, 2017). Edward Deming introduced a revolutionary management philosophy, placing quality as the critical factor for success. Using statistical tools, Deming's research took quality control to a higher level. According to Deming, the main factors in quality management include customer satisfaction, employee involvement, and continuous improvement. Deming's contributions pioneered quality management and paved the way for significant developments in quality-focused management approaches (Khorasani & Almasifard, 2017).

In the 1960s, the organizational environment was discussed for the first time through research by Katz and Kahn (1966). Early influences on the concept of organizations as open systems formed the basis for further study, as expressed by (Davis and Powell, 1992). This theory explains that the organizational environment consists of forces, conditions, and outside influences. These environmental impacts greatly influence managers' ability to manage resources. Organizational environmental theory also reflects interdisciplinary research that combines organizational concepts with the fields of ecology, demography, and other environmental sciences. The main focus is the link between organizational studies and global issues such as sustainability and ecological aspects in production. Attention to sustainability and environmental elements in production has become a significant global issue.

The development of economics increasingly follows the times, following technological developments even today. One of the developments in management theory from the previous period was agency theory. This approach is also known as the

situational approach and was developed by managers, consultants, and researchers who sought to apply concepts from primary management schools to real-life situations. In previous management science research efforts that applied these concepts to real problems, some ideas that were effective in one case failed in another, so it can be concluded that the results were different because the conditions were different. In other words, a technique that works in one case will only sometimes work in some cases (Agogbua et al., 2017). Therefore, the contingency approach to management emphasizes that there is only one best way to manage people or work in every situation. Managers should study individual and situational differences before deciding what actions to take. These differences can be noted due to the different environmental and organizational needs and structures that influence organizations, coupled with differences in resources and capabilities associated with individual organizations (Agogbua et al., 2017).

Apart from agency theory, there is also a theory obtained from the evolution of management science, namely corporate governance theory. This governance process was introduced during the time of Henri Fayol. Where according to Fayol, governance is the process of managing a company towards the desired goals by making the best possible use of all available resources and ensuring the smooth running of the six functions of industrial activities such as commercial, financial, security, accounting, managerial and technical (Fayol, 2013; Wren, 2001). Fayol's thoughts were based on his experience in management-level company positions. Fayol's management function can also be applied to the formation of governance in the educational sector, such as universities and schools with several departments where there are lines of coordination between departments (Otieno, 2019). Every organization with an organizational structure has duties and responsibilities for each division, and the management of these divisions uses Fayol's six management functions, such as the planning process, organizing, and directing. Nairobi, Kenya, is one university that implements a governance process using Fayol's management science. The university has a learning plan for each new year, which is the most critical stage. The program comes from university leaders and officials and is accompanied by the next financial budget plan. At this stage, almost every employee is monitored, work is evaluated, and job duties and assignments are reviewed. All official communications from head office are shared and ensure work is progressing according to approved plans and budgets (Otieno, 2019).

The application of Fayol's management science has benefits for the application of corporate governance; this is because corporate governance is related to the relationship between managers, the board of directors, employees, controlling parties, majority shareholders, and other stakeholders (Wahyudin & Solikhah, 2017). (Buallay, 2019) also believes that corporate governance refers to how a company should be run, regulated, and controlled. The main goal of corporate governance is to improve company performance by supervising or monitoring management performance and the accountability of other stakeholders based on the applicable rules and regulations framework.

In Indonesia, the management system is considered to have deep roots in culture since ancient times, reflecting participatory values, as seen in the practice of cooperation. However, the colonial period by the Dutch and Japanese also influenced management patterns in Indonesia. For example, the government system with the People's Representative Council (DPR) follows the top-down approach implemented by the

Netherlands (De Zwart, 2012), while Japan introduced a clustering system with a bottom-up approach, forming community organizations from the bottom-level to the top level (Fukuhara, 2016). Although there are various views regarding the management system used in Indonesia, no model is specifically recognized as a management style that is original and unique to Indonesia, as seen in countries such as Japan, China, America, and Europe, which have models. Separate management. However, the management of state administration and business in Indonesia still needs to apply management concepts (Basuki et al., 2022).

Corporate governance also continues to develop in Indonesia. This can be seen from the fact that the Indonesian government has made great efforts to implement good corporate governance in the government and private sectors. This process includes establishing corporate governance institutions and legal changes to support the implementation of corporate governance. Even though there are improvements in corporate governance standards and regulations (International Finance Corporation, 2018), the practice still needs to be expanded to comply with the rules.

Many companies have conducted corporate governance assessments, but the evaluations focus more on establishing consensus and systems without ensuring their implementation has become a corporate culture (Saptono & Purwanto, 2022). Corruption cases in State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN) also show a mismatch between government efforts and the reality on the ground. Corporate governance is a long-term project that requires changes in corporate culture. However, the development of corporate governance in Indonesia occurred because the company failed to implement it. It is essential for the government as a regulator to provide adequate support and regulation to create an efficient and transparent market (Basuki et al., 2022; Saptono & Purwanto, 2022).

Implementing corporate governance is critical in the banking industry, especially when viewed from Henri Fayol's management principles. Fayol emphasized the basic principles of management, including initiative, remuneration, division of work, discipline, authority and responsibility, esprit de corps, and unity of direction. In the banking industry, where trust and integrity are essential, these principles are the foundation for achieving good performance (Harun et al., 2020). Apparent authority and strict discipline are necessary to ensure effective risk management, while unity of direction and command assist in making consistent and coordinated decisions. The subordination of personal interests to the public interest creates an environment where business policies and practices are developed by considering the interests of all stakeholders, including customers, investors, and society in general (Mukhibad et al., 2022). By implementing these principles through good corporate governance, the banking industry is expected to build a solid reputation, increase public trust, and ensure long-term sustainability in facing market dynamics and economic challenges.

Only a few previous research have discussed the development of Henri Fayol's management science in applying corporate governance in the banking industry. Previous research only discussed elements of power, such as the leadership of a Chief Executive Officer (CEO) in a company (Wayne Taylor, 2000), the importance of the relationship between the authority of the board of directors and its responsibilities (Buallay, 2019), the importance of disciplined behavior for employees in the industry. Banking (Reddy, 2009)

so that good togetherness will create effective collaboration in implementing governance (Boyt et al., 2005). More details about the study can be seen in Table 1 below. This

Table 1. Research Previous

Researcher Name	Year	Discussion result
Mukhibad	2022	Discuss not needing more responsibilities from the board of directors to authority possessed.
Aslam and Haron	2020	The CEO plays a vital role in bringing change and determining the direction of companies in the banking industry to reach expected goals.
Buallay	2019	Discuss connection needs more responsibility and authority regarding the delegation process and accountability in the human resource division industry banking.
Reddy	2019	Importance behavior disciplines employees in industry banking.
Chou and Buchdadi	2018	Discuss role formation committee remuneration. Give reasonable compensation so that it can have a positive impact on management.
Justin O and Brien	(2018).	Discuss the importance of behavior discipline in industry banking.
Mahindru	2018	Language about linkages with governance organization, where principles of order, remuneration, distribution work, and discipline are essential in creating an organized and efficient environment. It also discusses how good collaboration will create solid relationships and support decision-making.
Boyt	2005	Discuss behavior complete togetherness and passion for the industry banking will cause the team to feel connected To each other, pushing collaboration and creating a harmonious environment for fulfilling needs will alignment.
Wayne Taylor	2000	Discuss the CEO's role in implementing governance in the banking industry so that it produces effective performance processes.

However, the results of previous research should have discussed the relationship between Henri Fayol's management principles and the development of corporate governance in Indonesia's banking industry. This research is novel in examining the relevance of Henri Fayol's management principles, which have existed since 1930, to the implementation of corporate governance, especially in the banking industry sector. By discussing several of Henri Fayol's management principles, such as the unity of direction, authority and responsibility, remuneration, division of work, discipline, as well as esprit de corps and initiative, this research explores the extent to which these concepts remain instrumental and relevant in the dynamics of modern corporate governance. Involving

various researchers and researching over multiple years, this research analyses how these principles are realized in the current banking context, providing an in-depth view regarding the sustainability and adaptability of traditional management principles in facing the challenges of the times. Thus, this research provides an essential contribution to understanding whether Fayol's management foundations can still provide a solid foundation for corporate governance practices in the contemporary era, especially when facing the dynamics of the banking industry, which continues to develop.

Theoretical basis

Henri Fayol's Functions of Management

Henri Fayol put forward five essential functions in management, which he considered the main principles managers must carry out. The five management functions are planning, organizing, commanding, controlling, and coordinating.

Figure 2. Henri fayol's Five Functions of Management

a. The planning function is essential in establishing the company's vision and mission. The image reflects long-term goals, while the task is a strategy to achieve them. Fayol emphasized that planning is a complex process, directing the steps of entire departments and directly impacting the company's future (McNamara, 2009). Managers, to design practical plans, must consider tangible and intangible resources, as well as take into account work processes and future trends. Planning success is measured through unity, sustainability, flexibility, and specificity (Edwards, 2018). The planning function is crucial for a company because it is a guide to achieving goals, a basis for decision-making and risk management, and facilitates monitoring and evaluation (Rahman, 2012).

b. Then, the organizing function, which is the stage of organizing and redistributing resources to achieve company goals, involves a series of strategic steps in human resource management (Edwards, 2018). This process includes job identification, task classification, activity coordination, performance evaluation, and delegation of authority

and responsibility. Through this approach, companies can ensure that each department has the expertise to suit their needs, creating an efficient framework for achieving common goals (McNamara, 2009; Rahman, 2012).

c. Commanding function, or direction, is an integral part of the daily operational process that aims to ensure the smooth implementation of tasks (Edwards, 2018). This function involves providing direction and instructions to workers so that existing studies can be completed effectively and efficiently (Rahman, 2012).

d. The fourth function is controlling, as a supervisory function, playing a pivotal role in verifying that all tasks are carried out as directed. In addition, in producing goods or services, the control function guarantees that the quality meets predetermined standards (Edwards, 2018; McNamara, 2009; Rahman, 2012).

e. The final function is coordinating, which is a function to create working relationships between individuals and between divisions so that good synergy occurs. The coordination process is carried out to avoid communication chaos, unsupported worker vacancies, and so on (Edwards, 2018; McNamara, 2009; Rahman, 2012).

Henri Fayol's Principles of Management

This management principle establishes guidelines on how managers and subordinates behave in their work relationships. These guidelines consist of 14 management principles Figure 3, which aim to increase economic efficiency and effectiveness through training management in the required behavioral characteristics.

Figure 3 is a graphic representation of Henri Fayol's 14 principles of management, arranged in two columns. Each principle is numbered and accompanied by a small icon.

1		The Degree of Centralization			
2		Scalar Chain			
3		Order			
4		Equity			
5		Stability of Tenure of Personnel			
6		Initiative			
7		Esprit de Corps			

Figure 3 . Henri Fayol's Fourteen Principles of Management

An explanation of Fayol's fourteen principles of management is as follows in Table 2.

Table 2. Henri Fayol's fourteen principles of management

No.	Management Principles	A Brief Description
1	Division of Work	Break down work into smaller tasks to increase efficiency and specialization.
2	Authority and Responsibility	Authority must be accompanied by appropriate responsibilities to create order and effectiveness in the organization.
3	Discipline	Apply rules and sanctions fairly to ensure compliance and discipline within the organization.
4	Unity of Command	Each subordinate only takes orders from one immediate superior, preventing conflict and confusion.
5	Unity of Direction	To achieve consistency and efficiency, all organizational activities must be directed towards the same goal.
6	Subordination of Individual Interests	Individual interests must be placed below the interests of the organization as a whole.
7	Remuneration	Fair and appropriate pay for employee motivation and satisfaction.
8	The Degree of Centralization	The level of management centralization must be adapted to the needs and characteristics of the organization.
9	Rank Hierarchy / Organizational structure (Scalar Chain)	Establishment of tiers or levels of authority within the organization to ensure the efficient flow of information.
10	Equity	Fair and equal treatment to all organization members, creating a positive work atmosphere.
11	Stability of Tenure of Personnel	Reduce employee turnover to retain skills and increase productivity.
12	Initiative	Encourage employees to take initiative and make positive contributions in achieving organizational goals.
13	Esprit de Corps	Build team spirit and solidarity among employees to increase cooperation and productivity.
14	Order	Develop managerial decisions based on accurate and relevant information to achieve organizational goals.

Corporate Governance

Corporate governance can be explained as a system of rules and organizational structures that form the basis of ethical business operations. This system is considered a form of compensation for the various interests of stakeholders, which sometimes differ

from each other (du Plessis et al., 2018). Corporate governance involves multiple aspects within a company, including activities and rules, to ensure that the company complies with specific standards. This includes the regulations governed by the laws of the country in which the company operates, as well as the company's internal processes (Scherer et al., 2016). Therefore, the concept of corporate governance not only includes formal rules but also reflects the decision-making, direction, and control processes within the company. It includes all the elements that form the path to achieving the company's goals, as well as ways to measure and evaluate the results that have been completed.

Traditionally, corporate governance is defined as a model created to protect shareholder investments from managerial behavior that may be opportunistic (Roberts & Van den Steen, 2000). However, in recent years, the concept of governance has become increasingly widespread and applied to monitor various company activities, including their impacts on society and the environment. Additional aspects related to corporate sustainability often emerge in response to demands from multiple stakeholders. It cannot be denied that sustainability has now become an inseparable and crucial part of the strategy pursued by companies (Iansiti & Levien, 2004).

Research Methods

The research approach applied in this study adopted a descriptive qualitative analysis method. According to Sugiyono (2010), qualitative research methods are often referred to as naturalistic approaches because they are carried out in natural contexts or as ethnographic approaches, which are prevalent in cultural anthropology research. The emphasis on qualitative aspects arises because the data collection and analysis are in-depth. The data analysis method in this research, as described by Miles and Huberman (1984) and Sugiyono (2010), emphasizes an interactive process continuously until data satisfaction is reached. Data analysis activities involve stages of data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions or verification.

Discussion

The following discussion focuses on the development of management science discovered by Henri Fayol with the application of corporate governance in Indonesia. Government is increasingly developing in Asia, especially after the economic crisis that occurred in 1997. The financial crisis occurred in several Asian countries, such as Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia, and Thailand (Nam & Lum, 2006). For Indonesia, the economic crisis significantly affected the banking industry because, at that time, the banking industry had not yet implemented good corporate governance, had weak controls, and was still low in transparency. So, in 2001, the Indonesian government regulated regulations so that the Indonesian banking industry implemented governance processes effectively (Nam & Lum, 2006).

Governance in the Indonesian banking sector involves the application of management principles by Henri Fayol. These principles are esprit de corps and initiative, vital in creating harmony and shared direction within banking organizations. Meanwhile, remuneration, division of work, and discipline relate to efficiency and field, ensuring that wages are fair, the division of tasks is clear, and compliance with norms and rules is

followed. The principle of authority and responsibility ensures that the granting of power is accompanied by appropriate duties, forming the basis of an organizational structure that is accountable and focused on achieving common goals (Khan & Zahid, 2020). By implementing these principles, banking corporate governance can ensure efficient and fair operations, maximizing individual potential and initiative to achieve common goals.

Principle of Unity of Direction

One of Fayol's management principles, unity of direction, is vital in corporate governance. Research conducted by Fayol states that corporate governance is formed by an executive leader, a company strategic plan, and the company's vision and mission (Wayne Taylor, 2000). This process is called unity of direction because all these elements are interrelated. The leader of a company is usually named the principal director or chief executive officer (CEO). The CEO is crucial in implementing the "Unity of Direction" principle. They are responsible for formulating the organization's vision and mission, creating strategic communications, and making strategic decisions consistent with overall goals. In addition, the CEO must also ensure regular monitoring and evaluation of performance, establish an organizational culture that supports unity of direction, and empower the managerial team to achieve common goals. During organizational change, the CEO plays a vital role in leading the change and maintaining unity of direction amidst the dynamics of change that may occur (Aslam & Haron, 2020). This unity of law is not only limited to a top-down approach but must be implemented at all levels of the organization to achieve optimal effectiveness (Wayne Taylor, 2000).

Principle of authority and responsibility

The principle of "authority and responsibility" by Henri Fayol focuses on the importance of the relationship between authority and responsibility in organizations. In corporate governance, particularly in human resource management (HR), this principle determines how power is granted and responsibility is given to each individual in the organization (Buallay, 2019). HR management applies this principle by directing and assigning tasks to personnel. Clarity of the organizational structure is critical, and each section must have authority according to its responsibilities. Delegation of duties is an essential practice, allowing senior managers to distribute responsibilities to their subordinates.

Accountability is the main focus, where the granting of authority is also followed by responsibility for the decisions and actions of the directors (Mukhibad et al., 2022). So, this becomes the basis for performance evaluation and provides incentives for taking responsibility (Karsono, 2023). Implementing HR policies and procedures also requires giving authority to the human resources development (HRD) division. This is done so that the HRD division can make decisions in line with company policy and ensure compliance by all organization members (Adam & Suleiman, 2018). By understanding and applying the principles of authority and responsibility, human resource management can achieve higher levels of efficiency and effectiveness while ensuring that each organization member understands their role and is responsible according to their authority (Aslam & Haron, 2021).

Principles of Remuneration, Division of Work, Discipline

A company's activities relate to how the organization is structured and performs its functions. Operational processes emphasize more technical aspects of management work. How well human and material resources are utilized determines any organization's smooth and sustainable operation. The operational success of an organization can be achieved by reducing costs, such as time, money, and effort while increasing the results obtained from resource utilization. Management must continuously strive to create a competitive advantage by maintaining efficient arrangements of people and materials, complying with workplace rules and laws, directing efforts to specific tasks, and providing fair rewards as incentives for better results (Mahindru, 2018). The principle of order plays the most crucial role in these factors, followed by remuneration, division of work, and discipline. Hierarchy in an organization is realized by determining the appropriate arrangement of material and human resources. This aims to avoid material losses, save productive time, and reduce work-related conflicts. In addition, compliance with organizational rules, both implicit and explicit, is the primary key to smooth operations. Fayol (2013) emphasizes that discipline includes regulations made by employers and collective agreements between employers and employees or trade unions. Such an agreement is binding and satisfactory to both parties. These agreements, which form the basis of contemporary organizations, ensured good relations between superiors and subordinates and reduced union strikes, paving the way for continuous and unimpeded work.

According to Chou dan Buchdadi (2018), which discusses the formation of a compensation committee in the banking governance system that will improve the bank's performance, the construction of a remuneration committee that determines compensation for executive management has a positive impact. The remuneration committee will positively affect bank performance, such as increasing the company's market value, but this only affects large banks. Executive management will provide the best performance if given remuneration or compensation by improving company performance so that administrative leadership will better maintain their performance sustainably (Sari & Tjoe, 2017).

The principle of division of labor has a significant influence on corporate governance in the banking industry. In this context, this principle supports operational efficiency and clear responsibilities throughout the banking organization. By implementing a division of labor, banks can achieve greater specialization in areas such as risk management, lending, and compliance (GILANG et al., 2018). Well-defined responsibilities facilitate monitoring and supervision and strengthen accurate reporting systems. Additionally, the division of labor supports innovation and development because each unit can focus on solving specific problems and increasing skill levels. Overall, the principle of division of work contributes to creating an organized and efficient environment in the context of corporate governance in the banking industry (Mashitoh & Irma, 2013).

The principle of discipline significantly influences corporate governance in the banking industry. The field here is not just limited to enforcing rules but includes a work culture emphasizing obedience, ethics, and responsibility (O' & Brien, 2006). In the banking industry, the impact of the principle of discipline can be explained as ensuring

that banks comply with applicable rules and regulations, which is crucial for creating strong governance. High business ethics are built through disciplined principles, creating a positive reputation that maintains stakeholder trust (O' & Brien, 2006; Reddy, 2009). In addition, this principle determines how to resolve conflicts and ethical violations, including applying appropriate sanctions. Risk and security management processes and a disciplined culture help establish strict standards and procedures to reduce potential financial risks and keep customer data safe (JOHN et al., 2008). Disciplinary principles also shape employee behavior and responsibilities, creating an orderly and reliable work environment that supports effective corporate governance.

Additionally, discipline principles form the basis for effective internal monitoring and auditing, which helps ensure compliance with rules and catch non-conformities quickly (Hock et al., 2019). Providing sanctions and consequences for violations of disciplinary principles is an important step to ensure banking integrity and sustainability (Ferramosca et al., 2017). The focus on discipline plays a crucial role in shaping organizational culture and ensuring the implementation of effective corporate governance in the banking industry.

Esprit de Corps and Initiative Principles

The principles of Esprit de corps and initiative play a central role in meeting the need for harmony, fairness, security, and industry in the work environment (Mahindru, 2018). Esprit de corps, or community spirit, creates an atmosphere of solidarity among team or organization members (Fayol, 2013). With a strong fighting spirit (Korea), couples will feel connected to each other, encourage collaboration, and create a harmonious environment that supports the need for harmony (Boyt et al., 2005). Meanwhile, initiative refers to the ability and desire to take proactive steps, which is essential in achieving goals without explicit direction (Uzuegbu & Nnadozie, 2015). The existence of initiatives helps individuals find solutions, contribute actively, and improve conditions in the work environment. This principle can support the creation of justice, ensuring everyone has equal opportunities (Wren, 2001). Combining these two principles allows an organization to establish a positive and productive work culture (Adam & Suleiman, 2018; Edwards, 2018; Fayol, 2013).

The principles of esprit de corps (spirit of togetherness) and initiative have significant relevance in corporate governance in the Indonesian banking sector. A spirit of togetherness creates strong relationships among stakeholders, such as the board of directors, executive management, and shareholders (Lu & Wenchang, 2015). This harmony helps prevent conflicts of interest and supports cooperation in strategic decision-making (Wang & Zhang, 2018). Initiatives in corporate governance reflect the ability and desire to identify and respond quickly to challenges and opportunities (Nalukenge et al., 2018). These proactive steps involve complying with banking regulations, managing risk, and maintaining the institution's financial health. This linkage is also related to creating harmony and justice in the banking environment. A spirit of togetherness reduces the potential for internal conflict, creating a more harmonious environment (Mahindru, 2018). Initiatives, when wisely directed, ensure that decisions taken take into account the interests of all stakeholders, supporting the principles of fairness in corporate governance (Jaswadi et al., 2015; Wang & Zhang, 2018). Banks can improve transparency,

accountability, and overall performance by combining a spirit of togetherness and initiative in corporate governance practices (Hamid, 2022). This is crucial for maintaining stakeholder trust and ensuring sustainable business continuity in the Indonesian banking sector.

Several of Henri Fayol's management principles can be summarised from the discussion, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Summary of Discussion Results on the Application of Henri Fayol's Management Principles

Management Principles	Researcher Name	Year of Research	Discussion result
Unity of Direction	Wayne Taylor	2000	Unity of direction in corporate governance is seen as crucial, and corporate leaders, especially the CEO, have an essential role in implementing this principle to achieve optimal effectiveness.
	Aslam and Haron	2020	The CEO's important role in making changes and determining the direction of the company
Authority and Responsibility	Buallay	2019	This principle emphasizes the importance of the relationship between authority and responsibility within the organization, especially in human resource management (HR), with task delegation and accountability being the main focus.
	Mukhibad	2022	The responsibility for the directors' decisions must accompany the directors' authority.
Remuneration, Division of Work, Discipline	Mahindra	2018	Company activities are related to organizational governance, where the principles of order, remuneration, division of work, and discipline are essential in creating an organized and efficient environment.
	Chou and Buchdadi	2018	It is essential to establish a remuneration committee to provide reasonable compensation so that it can have a positive impact on management.
	Justin O and Brien, Reddy	2018, 2019	Discusses the importance of disciplined behavior in the banking industry

Management Principles	Researcher Name	Year of Research	Discussion result
Esprit de Corps and Initiative	Mahindru	2018	The principles of esprit de corps and initiative have significant relevance in corporate governance in the Indonesian banking sector, creating solid relationships and supporting fairness and industry in decision-making.
	Boyt	2005	In passionate togetherness, teams will feel connected to each other, encourage collaboration, and create a harmonious environment that fulfills the need for harmony.

Thus, Henri Fayol's management principles are still relevant in today's banking industry.

Theoretical Benefits

This research provides a valuable contribution to the theoretical understanding of management principles proposed by Henri Fayol, such as esprit de corps, initiative, unity of direction, authority and responsibility, remuneration, division of work, and discipline. This article discusses the application of Henri Fayol's management principles in corporate governance, especially in the Indonesian banking sector. It is emphasized that principles such as the unity of direction, authority and responsibility, remuneration, division of work, discipline, the spirit of togetherness, and initiative have solid theoretical relevance.

Applying these principles is essential for creating harmony and shared direction in banking organizations. The article highlights key elements such as clear structures, accountability, and compliance as critical factors in ensuring efficient and fair operations in corporate governance. In the context of risk management and innovation, the principle of division of labor is identified as a critical contributor to operational efficiency and transparent responsibilities in the banking sector. The principle of discipline is crucial in establishing a solid governance framework, including a work culture emphasizing obedience, ethics, and responsibility. A spirit of togetherness and initiative is integrated into corporate governance practices to meet the need for harmony, justice, security, and industry in the work environment. Both support forming strong relationships among team or organization members and encourage the ability to take proactive steps.

Applying these principles aims to achieve transparency, accountability, and better overall performance in the Indonesian banking sector, with a collaborative and proactive approach as the key to sustainable business continuity.

Practical Benefits

This research provides practical guidance for business practitioners, especially in the Indonesian banking sector, to apply Fayol's management principles to improve corporate

governance. This information can be the basis for developing more effective policies and practices in managing organizations.

As a basis for improving corporate governance in the banking sector, the information in this article can be used by governments, regulators, and other stakeholders to support policies and initiatives to strengthen the banking sector's governance and sustainability. The management principles explained in the previous section can help make better decisions at the executive and managerial levels. Organizational leaders can leverage these insights to shape policy, direct strategy, and ensure optimal operational efficiency. In addition, this research can increase awareness of the importance of corporate governance among company leaders and stakeholders. By realizing the positive benefits of applying management principles, organizations can be more open to change and improvement in their business practices.

The importance of unity of direction under executive leadership, especially the CEO, is highlighted in this research. The principle of authority and responsibility emphasizes task delegation and accountability as essential organizational practices. Additionally, job sharing is critical to achieving operational efficiency and supporting innovation in the banking sector. The principle of discipline enforces rules and creates a work culture emphasizing obedience, ethics, and responsibility. The combination of a spirit of togetherness and initiative is considered to create a harmonious environment, prevent conflict, and support taking proactive steps to achieve organizational goals. This practice is expected to increase transparency, accountability, and overall performance, maintain stakeholder trust, and ensure business continuity in the Indonesian banking sector.

This research provides practical insights that can help banking organizations optimize operations, achieve common goals, and maintain the trust of various stakeholders.

Conclusion

The development of management science discovered by Henri Fayol, especially in the context of corporate governance in the Indonesian banking sector, has significantly contributed to understanding and implementing management principles. Previous research has discussed the Indonesian banking sector, which experienced significant changes after the 1997 economic crisis, and the Indonesian government has realized the importance of implementing governance to overcome these challenges.

Fayol's management principles, such as esprit de corps and initiative, have proven to be relevant in creating a work environment that is harmonious, productive, and oriented towards common goals. In addition, the explanation of the principle of unity of direction provides insight into the critical role of the CEO in formulating the organization's vision and mission and ensuring alignment of leadership at all levels of the organization. The principle of authority and responsibility discusses the importance of power accompanied by appropriate duties to create an accountable organizational structure. It is also important to note that remuneration, division of work, and discipline significantly impact an organization's operations and culture. Fair pay, a clear division of labor, and a culture of discipline provide the basis for operational efficiency, employee empowerment, and sound risk management.

By combining these principles, good corporate governance can improve the Indonesian banking sector's transparency, accountability, and overall performance. This is a crucial step to maintain stakeholder trust and ensure business continuity amidst economic dynamics and changes in the business environment.

Suggestion

This research suggests that strengthening is needed in implementing the management principles proposed by Henri Fayol, such as esprit de corps, initiative, unity of direction, authority and responsibility, remuneration, division of work, and discipline. Implementing these principles can create a more efficient and purposeful work environment. It is then essential to increase the active involvement of all stakeholders, including the board of directors, executive management, and shareholders, in strategic decision-making. Strong engagement can build a spirit of togetherness and support a common direction toward company goals.

Furthermore, future research can discuss other Henri Fayol management principles, whether they can be applied to the banking industry governance system or research different industries besides banking.

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